

KOREAN MARTIAL ART AND TAEKWONDO HEALTH

¹Nasiba Rustamova Utkurovna, ²Turakulova Khilola Sayfiddinovna

¹ “Silk Road “International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

²Teacher, Department of Foreign Language and Global Studies Samarkand, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11223631>

Abstract. Taekwondo is a traditional Korean martial art with deep cultural and historic roots. This paper gives a summary of the fundamental aspects of taekwondo, including its origins, training methods, and benefits. It explores the significance of taekwondo as form of self-defense, a sport, and a means of cultivating physical and mental discipline. Moreover, it delves into the art's promotion of values such as integrity, perseverance, and respect, as well as its part in cultivating a sense of community and camaraderie among practitioners. Additionally, this paper examines the global popularity and ubiquity of taekwondo, emphasizing its positive impact on individuals, communities, and societies worldwide. Overall, this paper aims to offer a comprehensive understanding of taekwondo's rich heritage, its principles, and its enduring relevance in today's world.

Key words: Martial art; Physical fitness; Psychological health; Taekwondo, History and Development of Taekwondo.

Аннотация. Тхэквондо - традиционное корейское боевое искусство с глубокими культурными и историческими корнями. В этой статье дается краткое описание основных аспектов тхэквондо, включая его происхождение, методы тренировок и преимущества. В нем исследуется значение тхэквондо как формы самообороны, вида спорта и средства воспитания физической и умственной дисциплины. Более того, в нем рассказывается о том, как искусство продвигает такие ценности, как честность, настойчивость и уважение, а также о его роли в воспитании чувства общности и товарищества среди практикующих. Кроме того, в этой статье рассматривается глобальная популярность и повсеместное распространение тхэквондо, подчеркивается его положительное влияние на отдельных людей, сообщества и социумы по всему миру. В целом, цель этой статьи - дать всестороннее представление о богатом наследии тхэквондо, его принципах и непреходящей актуальности в современном мире.

Ключевые слова: Боевое искусство, Физическая подготовка, Психологическое здоровье, Тхэквондо, История и Развитие Тхэквондо.

Annotatsiya. Taekvondo-chuqur madaniy va tarixiy ildizlarga ega an'anaviy koreys jang san'ati. Ushbu maqolada taekvondoning asosiy jihatlari, shu jumladan uning kelib chiqishi, o'qitish usullari va foydalari haqida qisqacha ma'lumot berilgan. Taekvondoning o'zini himoya qilish shakli, sport turi va jismoniy va aqliy intizomni rivojlantirish vositasi sifatida ahamiyatini o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari, u san'atning yaxlitlik, qat'iyatlilik va hurmat kabi qadriyatlarni targ'ib qilishiga, shuningdek, amaliyotchilar orasida jamoatchilik va do'stlik tuyg'usini rivojlantirishdagi qismiga kiradi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqola taekvondoning global mashhurligi va hamma joyda mavjudligini o'rganib chiqadi va uning butun dunyo bo'ylab shaxslar, jamoalar va jamiyatlarga ijobiy ta'sirini ta'kidlaydi. Umuman olganda, ushbu maqola taekvondoning boy merosi, uning tamoyillari va bugungi dunyoda doimiy dolzarbligi haqida keng qamrovli tushuncha berishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Jang san'ati; Jismoniy tayyorgarlik; Psixologik salomatlik; Taekvondo; Taekwondo tarixi va rivojlanishi.

Taekwondo is a very popular martial art all around the world. The history of the development of Tae Kwon Do has been around for a long time and has changed and grown over the years, but there have been times when it was suppressed. The term Taekwondo is derived from the Korean term "Tae" implying foot, "Kwon" implying fist, and "Do" implying foot(path). So, literally, Taekwondo means "the path of the foot and the fist". In 1946, a group of martial artists formed the Korea Taekwondo Association to promote and develop a unified form of Korean martial arts. However, it wasn't until 1955 that the term "taekwondo" was officially coined. General Choi Hong-hi, one of the founding members of the Korea Taekwondo Association, played an important part in helping taekwondo grow and become popular. He also introduced the colored belt system, which is used to denote rank and proficiency. Throughout the latter half of the 20th century, taekwondo gained popularity both within Korea and internationally. It was shown as a trial sport in the 1988 Seoul Olympics and then became an official Olympic sport in 2000. Today, many people all over the world practice taekwondo and is known for its dynamic Olympic-style sparring competitions. Taekwondo came from Korea and is known as a martial art and a way of life. Understanding the history of taekwondo is an important part of learning about it. Tae Kwon Do is a type of fighting from Korea that focuses on using your feet and hands to kick, punch, and block. It also involves discipline and jumping. This martial art style helps train the mind and body; it focuses on building good character. In addition to its physical techniques, taekwondo also teaches people to be polite, honest, to keep trying even when it is hard, to control themselves, and to have a strong spirit. These beliefs are encouraged through following strict rules and intensive training, with the goal of developing both physical and mental strength in practitioners. This article will explore the positive influences of taekwondo on aerobic fitness, reaction time, and psychological health.

Taekwondo is a martial art that requires a high level of aerobic fitness. Being aerobically fit means that our body is good at using oxygen when we exercise. It involves the efficiency of the cardiovascular system, which includes the heart, lungs, and blood vessels. In taekwondo, aerobic exercises are incorporated into training sessions to improve endurance, stamina, and cardiovascular fitness. These exercises include activities such as running, jumping jacks, high kicks, and various kicking and punching combinations. Regular taekwondo training routines can significantly improve aerobic fitness. They involve dynamic movements that require bursts of energy, which can increase heart rate and improve cardiovascular endurance. Additionally, the repetitive kicking and punching actions during training help increase lung capacity. Improved aerobic fitness in taekwondo can lead to several benefits, for example enhanced endurance, increased stamina, quicker recovery, improved overall health. It is important for taekwondo practitioners to incorporate aerobic exercises into their training routine and gradually increase the intensity to improve aerobic fitness progressively. Richman and Rehberg(1986) , “suggest that traditional martial art have survived and even `grown` over the years not only because of their cultural and historical importance , but also because of their physical and psychological benefits”.

Everyone need to be self-confident and self-esteem in our life. “Learning traditional martial arts can make people less aggressive, less anxious, and better at controlling themselves”, according to Zivin et al (2001). Taekwondo helps people become healthy and feel better, both physically and mentally. Taekwondo is likely based on evidence. “Going to school can make college women feel better about themselves (Finkenberg ME. 1990 as cited Fong & SMNG, 2014), decrease anxiety in adults (Kurian M, Caterino LC, Kulhavy. 1993 as cited Fong & SMNG, 2014), help kids manage their behavior and behave well in school (Lakes KD, Hoyt W. 2004 as cited Fong & SMNG ,2014),

encourage good feelings in college students (Toskovic NN.2001 as cited Fong & SMNG, 2014) and even reduce juvenile delinquent tendencies” (Trulson ME.1986 as cited Fong & SMNG, 2014). Today, “hear a lot about a child’s self-esteem. Unfortunately, experts do not understand real confidence”. Case in point, athletic programs are structured, so there are no "losers". School curriculums are designed so that no one is "left behind". In a somewhat misguided approach, people try to give kids self-confidence. The reality is that children need to find it on their own. Esteem needs to stem from confidence in real abilities. When your child takes Tae Kwon Do classes, they build self-confidence the right way. Franklin Delano Roosevelt said that having trust and being honest go together. “Confidence grows when we are honest, honorable, keep our promises, protect others, and help without expecting anything in return. If it does not have them, it cannot survive.”- Franklin D. Roosevelt. This means that being truthful, having good character, and controlling yourself are important for feeling good about yourself. all of these things are very important for a person who practices martial arts. Tae Kwon Do teaches kids to always keep their promises. They learn to be polite and honest. Knowing that people trust them makes them feel good about themselves. Progress in rank involves proven character traits as well as physical prowess. Once more, they feel sure of themselves because of things they really did, not made-up situation. Tae Kwon Do makes leaders, not followers. Self-assurance helps people become leaders. Research has found that people who learn martial arts feel surer of themselves and become better at protecting themselves. People who are bullied feel braver when they learn how to solve problems and protect themselves if they need to. Nearly two-thirds of children who are being bullied no longer have a problem once they reach black belt status. Tae Kwon Do does not only help people who are bullied. Bullies do not feel good about themselves, so they pick on others to feel better.

One of the important parts of taekwondo is reaction time. Reaction time tell us how quickly our body can respond to things and is a clue to how likely we are to get hurt while playing sport. Therefore, it’s an important way to know how healthy athletes are, whether they are professionals or just play for fun (Nakamoto H.& Mori S. 2008 as cited in Fong & SMNG, 2014). The reaction time of a taekwondo practitioner can vary depending on the individual. However, in general, taekwondo practitioners develop quick reaction times through training and practice. Taekwondo emphasizes speed and agility, so practitioners work on improving their reflex, timing, and ability to anticipate and respond to their opponent`s movements. Through drills, sparring, and competitions, taekwondo practitioners train their sensory perception and develop quick reflex. There are two sorts of response time: straightforward and choice. Basic response time is the period between the appearance of a common boost to the onset of drive generation by the comparing muscles. It is primitive and cannot be trained (Mori S.& Ohtani Y.& Imanaka K.2002 as cited in Fong & SMNG, 2014). Choice reaction time is how quickly someone can respond to one thing out of many things (Scmidt RA. 1990 as cited in Fong & SMNG, 2014). Overall, taekwondo training works to enhance a practitioner`s ability to react swiftly and effectively in a combat situation.

In conclusion, taekwondo is a martial art that encompasses physical, mental, and ethical components, making it a holistic discipline that benefits individuals both physically and mentally. Its emphasis on self-disciple, respect, and perseverance fosters personal development and growth. The practice of taekwondo promotes physical fitness, self-defense skills, and mental resilience, contributing to improved overall well-being. Taekwondo is a well-known martial art that is important around the world. It helps people from different cultures understand and learn from each

other. Its combination of tradition, philosophy, and athleticism makes it a valuable discipline for individuals of all ages.

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